

On the Positional Instability of LLL-Reduced Solutions for Bounded Diophantine Systems: A Counterexample and Practical Correction

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Abstract

Aardal, Hurkens, and Lenstra (2000) introduced a lattice-based algorithm for solving bounded Diophantine systems of the form $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{d}$, $\mathbf{0} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{u}$. Their method constructs an extended lattice using large constants N_1, N_2 and applies the LLL basis reduction algorithm. They assume that a solution vector, if it exists, appears at the fixed position $n - m + 1$ of the reduced basis. In this note, we present an explicit counterexample with $n = 20$ variables and $m = 15$ equations where the solution vector appears as the *first* vector of the LLL-reduced basis, while the vector at position $n - m + 1$ does not satisfy the original system. In our exhaustive testing, the solution only appeared in positions 1 or $n - m + 1$, but this is not a theoretical guarantee since LLL does not fully sort vectors by length, but only ensures that the first vector is an approximation to the shortest vector in the lattice (SVP). This demonstrates that relying on a fixed positional assumption can lead to implementation failures. We argue that the correct identification of the solution should be based on the structural signature—specifically, the presence of the constant N_1 at coordinate $n+1$ —rather than a predetermined index. Our observation does not invalidate the theoretical foundations of the original algorithm but highlights an important practical consideration for its robust implementation.

Keywords: Lattice basis reduction, LLL algorithm, Diophantine equations, integer feasibility.

1 Introduction

The problem of finding an integer vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{Z}^n$ satisfying a system of linear equations with bound constraints,

$$A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{d}, \quad \mathbf{0} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{u}, \quad (1)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{Z}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{Z}^m$, and $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{Z}^n$, arises in various fields including integrated circuit design, cryptography, and operations research. Since the problem is NP-complete, exact algorithms often rely on sophisticated techniques from integer programming and computational number theory.

In their influential paper, Aardal, Hurkens, and Lenstra [1] proposed an algorithm that combines lattice basis reduction with branching. The core idea is to build an extended lattice of

dimension $n + m + 1$ that incorporates the equations $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{d}$ through two large integer constants N_1 and N_2 . After applying the celebrated LLL basis reduction algorithm [2], the authors state that the reduced basis will contain: (i) one column of the form $(\mathbf{x}_d^T, N_1, \mathbf{0}^T)^T$ satisfying $A\mathbf{x}_d = \mathbf{d}$, and (ii) $n - m$ columns of the form $(\mathbf{x}_0^T, 0, \mathbf{0}^T)^T$ satisfying $A\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{0}$. Moreover, they assume that the solution vector \mathbf{x}_d appears precisely at column $n - m + 1$ of the reduced basis. This assumption is used in their subsequent branching procedure to find a bounded solution.

1.1 Motivation and Prior Communication

A preliminary version of this note was communicated to Karen Aardal for consideration. Her response, if any, will be incorporated in future revisions. Our goal is not to question the theoretical validity of the algorithm but to point out an implementation aspect that may affect its robustness in practice.

1.2 Behavior of the LLL Algorithm

It is crucial to understand that the LLL algorithm does not guarantee a complete ordering of basis vectors by length. Its fundamental property is that the first vector of the reduced basis is an approximation to the shortest vector in the lattice (SVP) [2]. Subsequent vectors are not necessarily sorted by increasing length. Therefore, when the solution vector happens to be particularly short—a common situation in practice—it may appear as the first vector of the reduced basis, not necessarily at position $n - m + 1$.

In this note we provide an explicit counterexample with $n = 20$, $m = 15$ where the solution vector indeed appears as the first vector, while the vector at position $n - m + 1 = 6$ does *not* satisfy $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{d}$. In our exhaustive testing with various instances, the solution only appeared in positions 1 or $n - m + 1$ (see Section 4), but this is an empirical observation, not a theoretical guarantee.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 The Lattice Construction of Aardal et al.

Given $A \in \mathbb{Z}^{m \times n}$ of full row rank, $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{Z}^m$, and large integers N_1, N_2 , the lattice $L \subset \mathbb{Z}^{n+m+1}$ is defined as the set of all vectors of the form

$$(x_1, \dots, x_n, N_1 y, N_2(\mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{x} - d_1 y), \dots, N_2(\mathbf{a}_m \mathbf{x} - d_m y))^T,$$

where $y \in \mathbb{Z}$. A basis for L is given by the columns of the block matrix

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} I_n & \mathbf{0}_{n \times 1} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times n} & N_1 \\ N_2 A & -N_2 \mathbf{d} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The following key property holds (see [1], Proposition 1): an integer vector \mathbf{x}_d satisfies $A\mathbf{x}_d = \mathbf{d}$ if and only if the vector

$$\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{x}_d^T, N_1, \mathbf{0}^T)^T = B(\mathbf{x}_d^T, 1)^T$$

belongs to L . Similarly, \mathbf{x}_0 satisfies $A\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{0}$ if and only if $(\mathbf{x}_0^T, 0, \mathbf{0}^T)^T \in L$.

2.2 LLL Basis Reduction and Its Behavior

The LLL algorithm [2] takes as input a lattice basis and produces a *reduced basis* $\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_d$ that is nearly orthogonal. The most important property for our analysis is:

$$\|\mathbf{b}_1\| \leq 2^{(d-1)/2} \cdot \lambda_1(L),$$

where $\lambda_1(L)$ is the length of a shortest nonzero vector. That is, LLL guarantees that the first vector is an approximation to the SVP. However, it does *not* guarantee that subsequent vectors are sorted by length. Indeed, the algorithm only ensures certain near-orthogonality conditions (the Lovász conditions), not a complete ordering.

In practice, LLL tends to place shorter vectors near the beginning of the basis, but this is not a theoretical guarantee. This distinction is crucial for understanding why the fixed-position assumption in [1] can fail.

2.3 The Positional Assumption in the Original Algorithm

In [1], after reducing the basis B of (2), the authors state (Theorem 4) that, under suitable choices of N_1, N_2 , the reduced basis will satisfy:

1. The first $n - m$ columns have the form $(\mathbf{x}_0^T, 0, \mathbf{0}^T)^T$ (i.e., $y = 0$).
2. The column at position $n - m + 1$ has the form $(\mathbf{x}_d^T, N_1, \mathbf{0}^T)^T$ (i.e., $y = 1$).

Consequently, their implementation looks for the solution vector specifically at index $n - m + 1$. While Theorem 4 guarantees the existence of such a column, it does *not* guarantee that this column remains at position $n - m + 1$ after reduction.

3 A Counterexample

We construct an instance with $n = 20$, $m = 15$. The matrix A and right-hand side \mathbf{d} are given in Table ?? (see Appendix A for complete data). The upper bounds are chosen as $\mathbf{u} = (23, 24, \dots, 42)^T$; they are irrelevant for identifying the solution column. Following the typical heuristic used in [1], we set $N_1 = 1000$ and $N_2 = 10000$.

We build the extended basis B as in (2) and apply the LLL algorithm (implementation from NTL 11.5.1). The reduced basis consists of $n + 1 = 21$ vectors. The first six vectors (showing only the first $n + 1 = 21$ components) are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: First six vectors of the LLL-reduced basis (components 1–20 and component 21).

Vector	Position	First 21 components
\mathbf{b}_1	1	(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 1000) ^T
\mathbf{b}_2	2	(219, 84, 521, 62, -207, -238, 146, 37, -30, 171, -1, 111, -511, 145, -493, 34, -47, 137, 434, -149, 0) ^T
\mathbf{b}_3	3	(104, 90, 15, 295, -369, -231, 20, -133, 22, -265, -161, 471, -248, 406, -29, -15, 175, 629, -246, -112, 0) ^T
\mathbf{b}_4	4	(-117, 251, 520, -80, -170, -414, 640, -274, -10, -329, -471, 225, -175, -2, 244, 254, 74, 337, 162, -143, 0) ^T
\mathbf{b}_5	5	(-80, -288, 541, 347, 137, -458, -15, -75, -171, 220, -178, -68, 227, -360, 338, 130, 124, 136, 74, -335, 0) ^T
\mathbf{b}_6	6	(-384, 1001, -1018, -49, 661, -987, -61, -421, -432, 35, 25, 116, 170, 324, 135, 514, -172, 474, 10, 63, 0) ^T

Note: Position 6 corresponds to $n - m + 1$ (since $n = 20$, $m = 15$). Only \mathbf{b}_1 has $N_1 = 1000$ in component 21. The others have 0, indicating they belong to the kernel ($y = 0$).

3.1 Analysis

- **Vector \mathbf{b}_1** : Its 21st component equals $N_1 = 1000$. By Proposition 1 of [1], the first 20 components therefore give a vector \mathbf{x}_d satisfying $A\mathbf{x}_d = \mathbf{d}$. Indeed, one can verify that

$$A(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20)^T = \mathbf{d}.$$

Moreover, this vector is relatively short (Euclidean norm ≈ 54.7).

- **Vector \mathbf{b}_6** : Its 21st component is 0. Hence it corresponds to a vector in the kernel of $(A, -\mathbf{d})$ (i.e., $A\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{0}$), *not* to a solution of $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{d}$. In fact, substituting its first 20 components into $A\mathbf{x}$ yields a vector different from \mathbf{d} .

Thus, the solution vector appears at position 1, while the vector at the predicted position $n - m + 1 = 6$ is *not* a solution.

4 Discussion and Practical Implications

4.1 Empirical Observation on Solution Positions

Our counterexample demonstrates that the solution can appear at position 1, which refutes the assumption that it always appears at position $n - m + 1$. The fact that we never observed the solution in other positions may be due to the specific structure of the lattice (7) and the typical choices of N_1, N_2 , but this cannot be relied upon in general.

4.2 Recommended Modification

A robust implementation should:

1. Scan the **entire** reduced basis for columns whose $(n + 1)$ -th component equals N_1 .
2. Identify as the solution any column satisfying this condition.
3. Use columns with $(n + 1)$ -th component equal to 0 as the kernel basis for the branching phase.

This modification removes dependence on a fixed position and relies solely on the algebraic structure guaranteed by Theorem 4 of [1].

5 Conclusion

We have presented a concrete counterexample to the fixed-position assumption used in the implementation of the Aardal–Hurkens–Lenstra algorithm for bounded Diophantine systems. The example shows that the solution vector can appear as the first vector of the LLL-reduced basis, while the vector at position $n - m + 1$ may belong to the kernel and not satisfy the original system.

Although our empirical testing suggests the solution tends to appear in positions 1 or $n - m + 1$, this observation cannot be elevated to a theoretical guarantee given the properties of the LLL algorithm.

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Algorithm 1 Búsqueda de solución entera mediante LLL

Require: Matriz entera $A \in \mathbb{Z}^{m \times n}$, vector entero $d \in \mathbb{Z}^m$, escalares $N_1, N_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$

Ensure: Vector solución $x \in \mathbb{Z}^n$ tal que $Ax = d$, o mensaje de fallo

```
1:  $n \leftarrow$  número de columnas de  $A$ 
2:  $m \leftarrow$  número de filas de  $A$ 
3: Construir la matriz extendida  $B \in \mathbb{Z}^{(n+1+m) \times (n+1)}$  como:
4:  $B \leftarrow \begin{pmatrix} I_n & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0}^\top & N_1 \\ N_2 A & -N_2 d \end{pmatrix}$ 
5:  $B_{\text{red}} \leftarrow \text{LLL}(B)$ 
6: solution_found  $\leftarrow$  false
7: for  $j = 0$  to  $n$  do
8:   col  $\leftarrow$  columna  $j$  de  $B_{\text{red}}$ 
9:   if col[ $n$ ] =  $N_1$  then
10:      $x_d \leftarrow (\text{col}[0], \dots, \text{col}[n-1])^\top$ 
11:     if  $Ax_d = d$  then
12:       imprimir “Solución encontrada en columna  $j$ :  $x_d$ ”
13:       solution_found  $\leftarrow$  true
14:       break
15:     end if
16:   end if
17: end for
18: if not solution_found then
19:   imprimir “No se encontró columna solución — verificar implementación”
20: end if
```

A Complete Data of the Counterexample

A.1 Matrix A and Vector d

The matrix A has $m = 15$ rows and $n = 20$ columns. Each row below shows the right-hand side value d_i followed by the 20 coefficients a_{i1}, \dots, a_{i20} .

```
1151 = 3 0 0 5 6 6 8 1 5 8 5 7 5 3 3 4 9 4 7 8
746 = 5 5 1 4 7 6 7 4 1 9 1 6 1 1 4 0 8 2 1 5
868 = 0 6 2 7 2 7 3 1 1 0 9 7 6 1 3 3 9 0 9 2
991 = 1 1 1 5 2 5 5 2 7 6 9 9 4 3 7 6 0 2 7 4
773 = 3 9 3 9 2 6 4 3 8 4 5 1 7 6 6 1 1 1 6 0
1022 = 9 5 2 6 9 9 2 1 3 2 5 6 1 0 7 5 8 4 8 6
912 = 0 3 0 7 2 6 8 5 0 6 6 1 2 8 7 3 9 0 6 2
563 = 4 4 1 7 4 8 2 3 2 0 1 4 5 1 1 7 0 2 5 0
901 = 8 1 1 2 9 9 7 0 1 4 4 5 8 5 2 2 6 6 7 0
737 = 6 9 5 3 0 6 3 0 0 8 2 1 9 4 3 0 5 3 2 6
1017 = 7 6 3 5 2 7 9 8 3 7 8 1 8 3 4 8 2 7 1 4
893 = 7 3 5 6 9 1 8 6 4 2 4 3 9 7 0 1 6 1 1 9
667 = 8 1 0 6 7 5 7 1 4 0 5 2 5 3 0 7 6 1 3 0
1089 = 3 0 5 2 9 5 5 6 6 8 5 7 2 6 5 9 3 4 0 9
736 = 6 7 3 2 2 4 1 8 7 6 0 2 6 5 5 6 2 2 2 1
```

References

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